

Fabrication, characterization and application of carbon ceramic nanocomposite prepared by using multiwalled carbon nanotubes and organically modified sol-gel glasses

Ida Tiwari^{*a}, Manorama Singh^{a,b} and K. P. Singh^a

^aDepartment of Chemistry (Centre for Advanced Study), Faculty of Science, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221 005, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : idatiwari_2001@rediffmail.com

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Guru Ghasidas Vishwavidyalaya, Bilaspur-495 009, Chhattisgarh, India

E-mail : manoramabhu@gmail.com

Manuscript received online 18 January 2014, revised 25 February 2014, accepted 01 March 2014

Abstract : We herein report the development of carbon ceramic nanocomposite nanoelectrodes by incorporation of multiwalled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) in organically modified sol-gel glass (Ormosil) matrix which is derived from silane precursors, 3-glycidoxypropyltrimethoxysilane, tetraethoxysilane and 3-aminopropyltrimethoxysilane. The different ratios of the silanes precursors, temperature, and gelation time were all optimized in order to obtain a stable and reproducible film. The ceramic composite was modified with the incorporation of MWCNTs, a redox mediator ferricyanide and the enzyme Horseradish peroxidase (HRP). Characterization of the ceramic composite was performed with scanning electron microscopy (SEM), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), atomic force microscopy (AFM) and cyclic voltammetry (CV). The ceramic composite sensor was explored towards the sensing of hydrogen peroxide providing a useful electroanalytical performance.

Keywords : Ormosil, ceramic nanocomposite, multiwalled carbon nanotubes, HRP.

Introduction

Organically modified siloxanes are organic inorganic hybrid materials which have been termed as 'Ormosils' or 'Ormocers' by Schmidt and 'Creamers' by Wilkes *et al.*^{1,2}, and are nanocomposites which have the potential for providing unique combination of properties which cannot be achieved by other materials³. As such, these hybrid materials have found application in many fields⁴. During the past 28 years, Ormosils have been widely prepared through the incorporation of organic additives in sol-gel processes. The sol-gel method is one of the most important techniques for the synthesis of various functional coatings or films, since it possesses a number of advantages over conventional film formation techniques, such as low temperature processing, easy coating of large surfaces, homogeneous film formation and good control of composition and optical properties of the final material^{5,6}. Another option is to move towards incorporation of organic molecules into the essentially inorganic matrix

using basically the same sol-gel technique. When organic groups are incorporated in the glass, the shrinkage is low since the bulky organic components fill the pores between the inorganic oxide chains. However, one single pure silane cannot generally make films thicker than 0.2 μm , since a large shrinkage of the film during the thermal densification process can easily cause cracking in a thicker layer. Moreover these prepared materials have low mechanical strength and low conductivity. Further problems associated with the electrochemical detection of molecules, namely high applied over potentials and fouling of the electrode surfaces, do not allow the majority of the biosensor based analytical devices to pass from academic concept to commercial applications⁷⁻¹¹.

The use of metal ions, carbon nanotubes and other additives with the organically modified alkoxide precursors may help to solve these problems and allow one to obtain a potentially useful material. Ormosils with nanocomposite additives are reported to be more

biocompatible and increase the electrical conductivity and long term stability of the developed biosensor⁶. Carbon nanotubes are promising nanomaterials due to their reported extraordinary physical and electrical properties such as high tensile strength, high elastic modulus, high thermal conductivity and electrical conductivity¹². The interaction of Ormosil with MWCNTs provides better nanoporous matrixes with high electrical conductivity for the immobilization of enzymes in its native state. The Ormosil/MWCNTs modified electrodes possess large potential windows with low and almost constant background currents and fast kinetics for a large number of electrochemical mediators⁴.

In the present work, 3-aminopropyltrimethoxysilane and tetraethoxysilane were the silanes chosen to control the hydrophobic and hydrophilic nature of the gelling system respectively whereas 3-glycidoxypropyltrimethoxysilane was used as reactive alkoxy silane precursors to develop an Ormosil. In the use of precursors, such as 3-glycidoxypropyltrimethoxysilane, there is a possibility of selective ring opening reactions in the presence of acids or bases. MWCNTs are then doped into the prepared Ormosil composition to prepare a ceramic nanocomposite. The composite developed has been characterized with SEM, TEM, AFM and cyclic voltammetry. The ceramic nanocomposite is modified further through the encapsulation of the mediator ferricyanide and enzyme HRP and is explored in the electroanalytical application of sensing hydrogen peroxide.

Results and discussion

Choice of alkoxy silane :

The choice of the alkoxy silane is the first parameter to be considered in order to successfully prepare an Ormosil. Silanes (precursors of the Ormosil) are a form of silica, which is a polar adsorbent that adsorbs polar solutes tightly¹³. Additionally, they form siloxane, after hydrolysis followed by condensation having highly complicated porous structure and stable chemical properties. 3-Glycidoxypropyltrimethoxysilane is an alkoxy silane with an epoxy group which is hydrolyzed to produce hydroxyl groups in the presence of water, which is followed by polycondensation of the hydroxyl groups at ambient temperature. Similarly the amino group of 3-aminopropyltrimethoxysilane helps to maintain the pH balance of the

medium preventing the protonation of other functional groups of immobilized materials in Ormosil matrix. Siloxane formed in the condensation and polycondensation reactions of TEOS as precursors are hydrophobic and can thus interact with the hydrophobic sidewall of the nanotubes through hydrophobic interaction.

Surface characterization of ceramic composite :

The study of surface morphology of the composite is an important factor because it affects the analytical performance of the fabricated biosensor. SEM, TEM and AFM are powerful tools to study the surface characterization of the fabricated composite and consequently we have investigated the surface study of the Ormosil using SEM [Fig. 1(A), (B), (C) and (D)]. Fig. 1(A) depicts SEM photographs of the Ormosil which shows the surface composition to comprise globular-type structures and appears rough. SEM images of the composite after incorporation with the redox probe potassium ferricyanide [*cf.* Fig. 1(B)] display a smooth and micro-porous surface. Fig. 1(C) SEM images reveal the composite surface following doping with MWCNTs and ferricyanide. In order to study the suitability of the prepared new Ormosil for biomolecule encapsulation, SEM images of HRP/Ormosil/ferricyanide/MWCNTs composite film were also obtained as shown in Fig. 1(D). As such, the uniform and open micro structured matrix should provide a significant increase in the effective surface for protein or enzyme loading and a good preparation reproducibility of the prepared biosensor.

Electrochemical studies of ceramic composite :

These ceramic composite have gained significant attention, as they are believed to be excellent for the immobilization of enzymes¹⁴. The results obtained on the investigations after the incorporation of enzyme HRP in the newly prepared ceramic composite material for the development of biosensor has been recently reported¹⁵. We investigated the electrochemistry of the ceramic composite. Fig. 2 depicts the cyclic voltammogram of the prepared electrode at various scan rates (5, 10, 20, 50 and 100 mV/s). It is evident from these observations that the incorporation of MWCNTs within the Ormosil improves the conductivity of the resulted film and facilitates the electron transfer among immobilized enzyme; mediator and electrode¹⁶.

Fig. 1. SEM of (A) plain Ormosil, (B) Ormosil/ferricyanide, (C) Ormosil/ferricyanide/MWCNTs, (D) HRP/Ormosil/ferricyanide/MWCNTs films.

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammograms of HRP/Ormosil/ferricyanide/MWCNTs composite.

The effect of varying scan rates (ν) on the peak currents was investigated in the range of 5–100 mV/s. When current was plotted against scan rates, the cathodic and anodic peak currents increased linearly with the increase of the scan rates with the equation of line being I_c (μA) = 0.843ν [$\mu\text{A}/(\text{V s}^{-1})$] + 0.978 ($R^2 = 0.99$) for cathodic

current and I_a (μA) = 0.751ν [$\mu\text{A}/(\text{V s}^{-1})$] - 0.847 ($R^2 = 0.98$) for anodic current respectively, suggesting that the electrochemical reaction is surface controlled process. Surface coverage (Γ) for the electro active species was estimated by using : $\Gamma = Q/nFA$, where A (0.70 cm^2) is the area of the working platinum electrode, n the number of

electron per reactant molecule, Q (3.69×10^{-6} C) the charge obtained by integrating the anodic peak at low voltage scan rate (10 mV s^{-1}), and F is the Faraday constant. In the present case, the calculated surface coverage for the electro active species was $2.93 \times 10^{-10} \text{ mol cm}^{-2}$. The electron transfer rate constant (k_s) of Ormosil/ferricyanide/MWCNTs modified electrode was estimated using the Laviron equation $k_s = mnFv/RT$ (when $\Delta E_p < 200 \text{ mV}$)¹⁷, where m is peak potential separation, v is the scan rate and rest have their usual meanings. The value of k_s is determined to be 21.6 s^{-1} [cf. Table 1].

Performance of sensor :

The analytical utility of the electrode was explored towards the electrochemical reduction of hydrogen peroxide; the response is displayed in Fig. 3. A linear response [$I_p (\mu\text{A}) = 0.734 (\mu\text{A}/[\text{H}_2\text{O}_2]) + 0.194 \mu\text{A}$, $R^2 = 0.99$] was displayed in calibration plot (cf. Inset to Fig. 3) with a linear response range between $8.0 \mu\text{M} - 6.0 \text{ mM}$. The biosensor has detection limit ($S/N = 3$) was found to correspond to $6.7 \mu\text{M}$ which is better than most of recent reported works. Comparison of present work with some other works¹⁸⁻²¹ is given in Table 1.

Table 1. Comparison of some analytical parameters with some other works

Sr. No.	Electrode	k_s (s^{-1})	Detection limit (μM)	Linear range	Sensitivity ($\mu\text{A}/\text{mM}$)	Ref.
1.	Hb-immobilized PAN-SiO ₂ /DTAB	0.91	30.0	0.09 to 2.8 mM	-	18
2.	CNT/Nafion/Na-montmorillonite	-	100.0	0.1-12.8 mM	1.71×10^5	19
3.	Graphene/Nafion/AzI/Au NPs/GCE	-	10.0	30 $\mu\text{M} - 5 \text{ mM}$	-	20
4.	Flowerlike ZnO-GNPs-Nafion	-	9.0	$15 \times 10^{-4} - 1.1 \text{ mM}$	-	21
5.	HRP/Ormosil/Ferr/MWCNTs composite modified Pt	21.6	6.7	8.0 $\mu\text{M} - 6.0 \text{ mM}$	0.73	Present work

Abbreviations : k_s - standard electron transfer constant, Hb - hemoglobin, PAN - polyaniline, DTAB - dodecyltrimethylammonium bromide, CNT - carbon nanotube, AzI - Azure I, AuNPs - gold nanoparticles, GCE - glassy carbon electrode, Ferr - Ferricyanide, HRP - horseradish peroxidase, Pt - platinum.

Fig. 3. Cyclic voltammogram of HRP/Ormosil/ferricyanide/MWCNTs modified Pt electrode in (a) absence of H_2O_2 and (b) in presence of $2 \text{ mM H}_2\text{O}_2$; Inset : calibration plot.

The electron transfer rate constant for HRP/Ormosil/ferricyanide/MWCNTs composite modified Pt electrode is also better than other work.

The stability of electrode was studied by the effect of observable changes obtained by cycling 20 repeated cycles in CV of HRP/Ormosil/ferricyanide/MWCNTs composite modified Pt electrode. The result justifies the stability of prepared electrode. When 20 continuous cycles scan was carried out at 10 mV/s scan rate, only 4.5% decrease of the initial response at 125 μM was recorded. The RSD of 2.5% was observed for three successive measurements of one modified electrode at 125 μM H₂O₂ indicating good reproducible behavior of the proposed sensor. The long term stability of the proposed sensor was also studied. Lifetime is more than 45 days when the electrode was kept at ambient conditions, when not in use.

In order to demonstrate the applicability of the proposed material for real sample analysis hydrogen peroxide was assessed in milk. We spiked milk sample with hydrogen peroxide and recovery studies were done. It was studied by standard addition method (Table 2). The results were also validated with spectrophotometric method. The milk sample without spiking does not give any detectable signal.

Experimental

Material and methods :

3-Glycidoxypropyltrimethoxysilane (3-GPTMS), 3-aminopropyltrimethoxysilane (3-APTMS) and tetraethoxy-

silane (TEOS) were obtained from Alfa Aesar (UK); MWCNTs (Aldrich, USA; purity 90%) were purified by heating in HCl (5 M) followed by ultrasonication for 30 min and rinsed with triple distilled water. Horseradish peroxidase (HRP) was obtained from Gennei, Bangalore, India. Hydrogen peroxide (30% w/v solution) was purchased from SD-fine Chemical Pvt. Ltd., India. Potassium ferricyanide was obtained from Merck, Germany. Aqueous solutions were prepared in triple distilled water. All other chemicals employed were of analytical grade.

Preparation of the Ormosil :

The compositions were optimized for practical applications based upon gelation time, cracking and stability of the Ormosil. The composition of different precursor solutions is summarized in Table 3.

Precursors' mixture was homogenized by continuous vigorous stirring followed by casting 10 μL of this solution on a glass slide. In all cases, gelation was allowed to occur at ambient temperature (25 °C). It was observed that composite film 1 and 3 is transparent whereas film 2 is opaque. The comparison of physical appearance, gelation time of the composite films and stability of composite films is shown in Table 4.

Hence, we can conclude composite film 3 is stable and transparent film and suitable for further use. Purified MWCNTs were ultrasonicated for 30 min in 3-glycidoxypropyltrimethoxysilane (0.1 mg/mL) prior to use at room temperature and composite film was prepared as summarized in Table 4 (film composition 3).

Table 2. Real sample analysis

Sr. No.	Standard added (mM)	Determined by spectrophotometric method (mM)	Recovery (%)	Measured by proposed biosensor (mM)	Recovery (%)
1.	0.5	0.498 ± 0.002	99.6	0.499 ± 0.001 (n = 3)	99.9

Table 3. Composition of Ormosil

Films	3-APTMS (μL)	3-GPTMS (μL)	TEOS (μL)	Ferricyanide (50 mM) (μL)	Water (μL)	HCl (μL)
1.	70	20	20	60	240	5
2.	70	40	40	60	240	5
3.	70	80	40	60	260	5

Table 4. Physical appearance, gelation time, stability of the Ormosil

Films	Temperature (°C)	Gelation time (h)	Physical appearance	Stability (in time)
Film 1	28	24	Transparent	1 h
Film 2	28	18	Opaque	45 min
Film 3	28	12	Transparent	> 12 h

Electrochemical characterization of ceramic composite :

Electrochemical characterization was performed with CH-instrument 630C series, USA. A single compartment cell with working volume of 4 mL with HRP/Ormosil/ferricyanide/ MWCNTs composite modified platinum electrode as working electrode, Pt wire counter electrode and Ag/AgCl reference electrode were used for the measurement. 0.1 M phosphate buffer of pH 7.0 was used as supporting electrolyte. The UV-Vis spectroscopic measurements performed with UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Hitachi, 3900), SEM of nanocomposite film has been performed with JEOL840A; Japan. TEM measurements were performed on a Tecnai G2 instrument. For TEM measurements the composite material was dispersed in distilled water and deposited onto a formvar/carbon coated copper grid.

Acknowledgements

The present research investigation has been funded by CSIR, New Delhi Scheme no. 01(1983)/05/EMR-II and BRNS, DAE. The authors are highly grateful for this financial support.

References

1. G. L. Wilkes, B. Orlor and H. Huang, *Polym. Prep.*, 1985, **26**, 300.
2. H. Schmidt, *J. Non-Cryst. Solids*, 1985, **73**, 681.
3. J. Wen and G. L. Wilkes, *Chem. Mater.*, 1996, **8**, 1667.
4. A. K. Upadhyaya, Y.-Y. Peng and S. M. Chen, *Sens. Actuat. (B)*, 2009, **141**, 557.
5. V. S. Tripathi, V. B. Kandimalla and H. Ju, *Sens. Actuat. (B)*, 2006, **114**, 1071.
6. I. Tiwari, M. Singh, V. S. Tripathi, G. Lakshminarayana and M. Nagomi, *Sensor Lett.*, 2011, **9**, 1323.
7. B. Lebeau, Guermeur and C. Sanchez, *Mater. Res. Soc. Symp. Proc.*, 1994, **346**, 315.
8. M. M. Collinson, *Trends in Anal. Chem.*, 2002, **21**, 30.
9. O. Lev and L. Rabinovich, *Electroanalysis*, 2001, **13**, 265.
10. O. Lev, Z. Wu, S. Bharthi, V. Glezer, A. Modestev, J. Gun, L. Rabinovich and S. Sampath, *Chem. Mater.*, 1997, **9**, 2354.
11. S. Iijima and T. Ichihashi, *Nature*, 1993, **363**, 603.
12. I. Tiwari, K. P. Singh, M. Singh and C. E. Banks, *Anal. Methods*, 2012, **4**, 118.
13. P. C. Pandey, S. Upadhyaya, B. C. Upadhyaya and V. S. Tripathi, *J. Sol. Gel. Sci. & Tech.*, 2005, **33**, 25.
14. A. F. Groboillot, C. P. Champagne, G. D. Darling, D. Ponelet and R. J. Neufild, *Biotech. Bioeng.*, 1993, **42**, 1157.
15. I. Tiwari, K. P. Singh, M. Singh, B. C. Upadhyay and V. S. Tripathi, *Anal. Lett.*, 2010, **43**, 2019.
16. V. B. Kandimala, V. S. Tripathi and H. Ju, *Biomaterials*, 2006, **27**, 1167.
17. I. Tiwari and M. Singh, *Microchim. Acta*, 2011, **174**, 223.
18. B. Chen, H. Wang, H. Zhang, Z. He, S. Zhang, T. Liu and Y. Zhou, *J. Molecular Liq.*, 2012, **171**, 23.
19. H. L. Hsu, J. M. Jehng and Y. C. Liu, *Mater. Chem. Phys.*, 2009, **113**, 166.
20. Y. Zhang, Y. Liu, J. He, P. Pang, Y. Gao and Q. Hu, *Electrochim. Acta*, 2013, **90**, 550.
21. C. Xiang, Y. Zou, L. Sun and F. Xu, *Sens. Actuat. (B)*, 2009, **136**, 158.